

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' INTELLECTUAL POTENTIAL AND SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPETENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7725922>

Abstract. *In this article, the role and importance of independent education in the development of students' intellectual potential and socio-cultural competence, the specific characteristics, advantages and tasks of independent work are shown.*

Keywords: *independent education, independent work, creative skills, creative work, handouts, module, skills, competence.*

The main task of education is the formation of a creative personality of a specialist capable of developing, educating and innovating people. It is difficult to solve this problem only by asking the teacher. It is necessary to turn the student from a passive consumer of knowledge into an active creator of knowledge who can thoroughly study the problem, analyze the ways to solve it, become an educator of the optimal result and prove its correctness. Currently, the educational reform is inextricably linked with the transition from the teaching paradigm to the educational paradigm. In this regard, it should be recognized that the student's independent work is not only an important form of the educational process, but also its basis, in addition to the knowledge given by the teachers during the teaching process.

First of all, it is necessary to clearly define what is the independent work of students. In general, this is any type of activity related to training the thinking of a future specialist. Any type of training that creates conditions for independent thinking and cognitive activity of the student is related to independent work. In a broad sense, independent work is understood as the sum of all independent activities of students both in the classroom and outside, in contact with the teacher and in his absence.

The purpose of independent education:

- strengthening and summarizing students' theoretical knowledge in their field;
- formation of students' skills and qualifications for independent mastery of the basics of science;
- development of cognitive activity, independent creative work skills and creative skills of students;
- consists of determining the skills of self-professional development and improvement of students and others.

The goal of students' independent work is their personal development in the process of acquiring new knowledge from various sources. Independent works include textbooks, educational manuals, scientific works of classics of psychology, monographs, collections of scientific articles and scientific lectures, scientific articles in specialized psychological magazines, psychological materials in periodicals, work with fiction. Recently, working with educational resources,

including the Internet system, computer programs, and information on educational carriers, has taken a large place in independent work. Students' independent works include writing essays, comments, theses.

The topic of independent education consists of lectures and seminar topics that students study independently. Including: the reflection of the image of a perfect human being in the work "Avesta", the unique coverage of educational issues in the writings of Kultegin, Bilga Haqan, Tunyuquq, the role of educational ideas in the legacy of Ahmad Yassavi, the educational importance of the scientific legacy of Abu Rayhan Beruni, Mahmud Kashgari's attitude to social education, Philosophical-pedagogical description of Omar Khayyam's creative heritage, Amir Temur's approach to spiritual-ethical and educational issues, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's spiritual-educational views, The perfect person and the issue of his upbringing in Alisher Navoi's interpretation, Husayn Vaiz Koshifi's moral views, the code of ethics summarized by Muhammad Sadiq Kashghari, the girls' school of Jahan Otin Uvaisi and Anbar Otin, the role of New Usul schools in the educational development, the services of Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhan's son in the field of education, XX Public education in Uzbekistan in the 1970s and 1980s, Independence and reforms in the education system, issues of spiritual education in the work of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov "High Spirituality - Invincible Power", Schools of Ancient Sparta and Athens experience, Johann Heinrich Pestalo's contribution to education, school-educational system, Johann Friedrich Herbert's edagogic views, in the French state lim system. Independent education helps students strengthen their theoretical knowledge, develop their ability to understand topics to the maximum extent, and expand their general outlook. Independent work of students plays an important role in the radical restructuring of the specialist training system and in increasing the importance of the educational process. The analysis shows that independent work is understood as such educational activity, in which, along with the acquisition of knowledge, the formation of skills is ensured. In practice, this is done in 4 independent work types depending on specific didactic goals. The first type of private-didactic purpose of independent work is the algorithm of activity, which, on the surface, consists of information and conditions of tasks, that is, to determine the skills that are formed in students and required of them based on the factors of the formation of initial knowledge (the first stage of knowledge). In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the tasks perceived by students. The second type of private-didactic purpose of independent work is the formation of knowledge aimed at processing the acquired information in memory and performing typical tasks, that is, the second stage of knowledge. The general description of all types of the second type of independent works is that in such works the idea (principle) of solving tasks is announced, methods and methods of developing this idea (principle) and applying it to concrete conditions are required from students. The third type of private-didactic goal of independent works consists of knowledge formed by students during the third stage - performing non-typical tasks. This goal can be achieved in the process of solving knowledge (perception) issues that require students to create algorithmic bases of the causes of changes in the studied object. The fourth type of private didactic purpose of independent works is to create factors for creative activity. The cognitive activity of students in performing such work is that students go deeper and deeper into the essence of the object under discussion, learn the necessary new, previously unknown ideas and solve the principles of creating new information. New connections build relationships. At the same time, the student is forced to puzzle over the essence of new actions and the nature of this or that information, which he has to create at each stage of performing

the tasks. In the literature on pedagogy, the following types of independent work are noted: independent work on samples; reconstructive-variative; heuristic (partial, creative); creative research. Independent work on samples is solving typical tasks, various exercises based on samples. They are a factor in mastering the material, but do not increase the creative activity of students. Reconstructive-variational independent work envisages not only the practical description of knowledge, but also the redevelopment of the structure of knowledge, the involvement of existing knowledge in solving a problem. Heuristic independent work is related to the solution of some issues and problems posed in lectures, laboratories, practical exercises, seminars. Research independent work aims at the ability to see a research problem, express it independently, determine a hypothesis, develop a plan for solving the problem, and solve it. Creative research work. In such cases, the task is to create conditions that require the emergence of a problematic situation. In his work, the student searches for ways to solve the problem, free from ready-made examples. Such work includes tasks related to the design of experiments, equipment, models and machines.

Independent work is carried out:

1. Directly in the course of audience training - lectures, practical and seminar training, laboratory work.
2. Out-of-hours contact with the teacher - during consultations on educational issues, in the process of creative communication, debt settlement, individual assignments, etc.
3. In the library, at home, in the dormitory, at the department, while the student is doing educational and creative assignments.

The development of a complex of methodical support of the educational process is the most important condition for the effectiveness of independent work of students. Such a set includes lecture texts, training manuals, laboratory exercises, assignments and task banks based on real data, calculation, modeling, training programs and self-management programs. , should include automated training and management systems, information bases of subjects related to a subject or a group, etc. This makes it possible to organize problem-based education where the student is an equal participant in the educational process.

The effectiveness of students' independent work is largely determined by the presence of active methods of its control. The following control types are available:

- Control of introducing students' knowledge and skills at the beginning of studying the next subject;
- Current control, that is, regular control of the level of mastering of the material in lectures, practical and laboratory sessions;
- Midterm control at the end of studying a course section or module;
- Self-monitoring performed by the student in the process of learning science in preparation for control activities;
- Final control of the subject in the form of a test or exam;
- To control the knowledge and skills that remain after a certain time after completing the study of science.

In conclusion, we note that specific methods and forms of organizing students' independent work, taking into account the course, the level of preparation of students and other factors, are determined in the course of the teacher's creative activity, so these recommendations cannot be universal . Their goal is to help the teacher to form his own creative system for organizing independent work.

In modern society, the tasks of a modern teacher are changing dramatically. The teacher becomes the organizer of the cognitive, transformative activity of students, who are not passive objects, but subjects of the educational process. Any new specialist should have fundamental knowledge, professional skills and abilities, experience of creative and research activities to solve new problems, experience of social and evaluation activities in his profile, because information is important for a person's professional development. is one of the influencing factors. Therefore, the success of an individual and the positive development of the whole society in general directly depends on the quality of the offered education. One of the indicators of educational success is the independence of students, which is necessary for the student to think and act independently in the process of overcoming educational difficulties. Therefore, the proper organization of students' independent work is one of the main factors of a successful future person.

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